

Numerical Investigation on the Consolidation Settlement Mechanism of the Soil with Multiple Layers

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ABSTRACT:

This parametric analysis shows different values of primary consolidation and secondary consolidation for the change in normal stress, number of years, footing size, clay layer thickness, D_f/B ratio, depth of bearing capacity obtained by "Geostru" software. It also shows the pressure increment values in clay layers for different normal stress. The research was done for six boreholes in three locations in Mymensingh, Sirajganj and Gazipur district of Bangladesh. The statistical analysis shows the values of slope, intercept, mean, standard deviation from the obtained data which will give a clear indication about the research outcome. The consolidation settlement graph for each parameter was plotted for each borehole which shows the regression value and correlation between the primary or secondary consolidation settlement with different parameters. The research clearly described the important findings and recommendations on shallow foundation for a particular area over soil with multiple clay layer.

Keywords: Consolidation settlement; Normal stress; Soil stratigraphy; Secondary consolidation settlement; Effective stress; Bearing surface depth; Parametric analysis.

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INTRODUCTION

A parametric analysis of consolidation settlement has been performed in this study using software analysis. Software analysis has been shown to be effective in numerous studies where practical in-situ testing is more difficult and time consuming. This chapter will provide a brief overview of consolidation settlement.

Research Background

A variety of theoretical, experimental, and numerical research on soft soil consolidation behavior have been done during the last few decades. The phenomena of clay consolidation are still the focus of a number of discussions. Recently, numerical and analytical solutions for the behavior of clay soils have been developed that consider a variety of influencing parameters and loading conditions [1,2,3]. However, reliable settlement calculations are still difficult to obtain by. The calculation of the consolidation settlement based on one-dimensional (1D) consolidation theory is still ongoing at the design stage, but the expected settlement reliability and soft ground pore water pressure have not

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yet achieved satisfactory levels. Comparative settlement estimated using 1D consolidation theory and measured on site settlement. However, in this study, the analysis will be done in three dimensions (3D), which will make software analysis much easier. Because calculations in 3D consolidation analysis are still considerably more complicated, we use the “GeoStru” software.

Consolidation is the compression of a saturated soil under a constant static pressure. It's totally due to water escaping from the voids. It works in the same way that squeezing water from a saturated sponge under pressure does. The soil acts like a saturated sponge. Water escapes during the consolidation of soils. Rolling and sliding causes the solid particles to shift from one location to another, resulting in a closer packing. It's worth emphasizing that the loss in soil volume is caused by the shifting of particle locations when water departs, rather than by solids or water compression. Small volume changes may occur as a result of solid particle bending, distortion, and fracture, although such changes are minimal in the normal range of stresses encountered in soil engineering problems. However, due to particle shifting, bending, distortion, and fracture are indirectly responsible for a further reduction in volume [4].

Figure 1. Consolidation

Where a building lies on a layer of low stiffness and low permeability soil, such as marine clay, the effects of consolidation are most noticeable, resulting in large settlement over many years. Consolidation theory that incorporates three-dimensional flow vectors is difficult and only applies to a small number of geotechnical engineering situations. It is necessary to consider that both seepage and strains occur in one direction only, which is usually vertical, for the great majority of practical settlement problems. Land reclamation, embankment construction, and tunnel and basement excavation in clay are all examples of building projects where consolidation creates a technical risk. Figure 2 shows a case of settlement. This is a picture of an unfinished building and failure the foundation.

Figure 2. Case of Settlement

- Consolidation settlement is very important in foundation engineering because it might cause damage to the structure over long period of time.
- The analysis will be conducted through “GeoStru” software, which is a finite element analysis software.
- Software analysis is essential to determine the variation and uncertain behavior of consolidation settlement.
- Theoretical and practical analysis are time consuming and limited where software analysis is proven effective.
- Secondary consolidation settlement depends on long time period. Practically it is not possible to wait 10 to 15 years to obtain amount of settlement so we use software modelling which will give accurate result instantly.
- This research is essential because it has a significant impact on foundation engineering. Since the dawn of civilization, foundation and geotechnical engineering have played an important role.

Objectives of the Research

The main objectives of the research are written below:

- Literature review of different types of consolidation settlement and their mechanism.
- Literature review of different approaches to consolidation settlement and their modelling.
- To determine the consolidation settlement on cohesive soil with software analysis.
- To analyze the variation of consolidation settlement due to change in soil layer, footing size and surcharge.
- To establish a correlation between related factors and parameters of consolidation settlement.

Parameters

Several parameters will be analyzed in this research:

- Change in consolidation settlement due to change in normal stress.
- Secondary consolidation settlement in number of years.
- Difference between settlement at corner and center of the foundation.
- Variation of pressure increment due to change in normal stress.
- Variation of consolidation settlement due to change in layer thickness.
- Variation of consolidation settlement due to change in D_f / B ratio (D_f = Depth of footing and B = Width of footing).
- Variation of Consolidation settlement due to change in footing size.

Correlation and graphical representation will be achieved between these parameters and consolidation settlement.

Structure of Thesis

Chapter 1: A brief introduction on consolidation settlement will be discussed on this chapter.

Chapter 2: This chapter provides the literature review of consolidation settlement, their parameters and also their related theory.

Chapter 3: In this chapter research methodology, software modelling and data entry procedure will be discussed as well as the parametric analysis will be done.

Chapter 4: A case study will be done in different locations of Bangladesh according to the application of chapter 2 and 3.

Chapter 5: Result analysis and result discussions based on the parametric analysis and case study will be done in this chapter.

Chapter 6: The conclusions and limitations of this research as well as the research findings will be summarized in this chapter.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A brief review of consolidation settlement, their parameters and also their related theory is presented in this chapter.

Current Status of Research and Future Tendencies

It is important to know what's going on in the world of consolidation settlement research. This will serve as a possible research guideline in the future work. Consolidated clay soil is often based on 1D conditions when calculating consolidation settlement and are still extensively applied due to the nonlinear pressure-strain relationship of clay [5]. Settlement can be calculated by consolidating uniformly loaded soils on an infinite strip of constant width and paying particular attention to the nature of the settlement at a loaded area's boundary, according to the general theory [6]. This study is based only on uniformly distributed load, and there is no consideration given to uniformly varied load in the analysis. During the process of squeezing, soil grains reorganize themselves into a more stable and dense form, which results in a reduction in volume and a reduction in surface settling [7]. The amount of consolidation of soft ground increases in direct proportion to the number of layers. However, unlike in the 1D condition, the ratio against correct settlement varies from 5.6% for one layer to 85.4% for ten layers, which is the same trend as in the 2D condition. As a result, the inaccuracy is substantially bigger than it would be under the 1D condition. As with the 1D condition, the increment of stress is consistent with depth in multi-layered situation. As a result, the increment of stress in each layer may be determined simply in the multi-layered case. As a result, under the 3D condition, the increment of stress can be calculated using either the 2:1 procedure or a theoretical solution for the semi-infinite elastic ground [7]. Squeezing of the pore fluid and steady increase in effective stress cause the clay to consolidate, which quickly leads to the circumstance that settlement is dependent on both stress and time. [8] analyze the soil's foundation, and the results of this analysis are dependent on the pore pressure set by the foundation load, and these pore pressures are dependent on the kind of soil, which is an approximation theory to describe the behavior of the soil. This study is based more on theory than the empirical evidence. More data analysis and statistical analysis are needed in this study in order to get the most out of it. Two Holocene coastal clays enhanced by a prefabricated vertical drain are studied to see whether the Constant Rate of Strain (CRS) consolidation test can be used to evaluate the stress-strain relationship of these clays' consolidation settlement [9]. The nonlinearity of the stress-strain relationship, which is only applicable to the maximum soil pressure, is taken into consideration in this study. It was determined in this study what influence the customary approach of determining the consolidation settlement of soft ground by separating the ground into one or more layers had on the results [10] The study did not find any evidence of a distinction between primary and secondary consolidation settlement under drained circumstances.

Effective Stiffness

It has been determined that the effective vertical stress (σ_v') at point A below the surface of the soil equals the stress applied by a solid on the soil at their point of contact (e.g., earth skeleton). This is calculated by subtracting the stress produced by the water from the total stress of the weight of the overlying material (σ_v) acting on the continuous void spaces in the overlying material (i.e., pore water pressure, u).

Figure 3. Effective Stress

$$\sigma_v = \sum \gamma_i Z_i \rightarrow \sigma_v = \gamma_w H + \gamma_{sat} H_A \quad (1)$$

$$u = \gamma_w Z_w \rightarrow \gamma_w (H + H_A) \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma'_v = \sigma_v - u \rightarrow \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma'_v = \gamma_w H + \gamma_{sat} H_A - \gamma_w (H + H_A) = (\gamma_{sat} - \gamma_w) H_A = \gamma' H_A \quad (4)$$

here,

$$\gamma_{sat} = \frac{W_s + W_w}{V_{total}}, \gamma' = \gamma_{sat} - \gamma_w = \frac{W_s}{V_{total}} \quad (5)$$

Consolidation

It is possible to reduce the bulk soil volume under loading due to the movement of pore water. The pore pressure will initially take up any increase in loading referred to as surcharge ($\Delta\sigma$) in saturated soils, resulting in consolidation until a new equilibrium is achieved at which the soil solids (or skeleton) will take up the additional load, at which point consolidation will terminate.

For cohesive soil,

at $t = 0$, $\Delta\sigma = \Delta u$; $t = \infty$, $\Delta\sigma = \Delta\sigma'$

Figure 4. Stress vs Time

Pre-Consolidation Condition and Time Rate of Consolidation

According to the geologic history, the soil is subjected to the greatest amount of effective previous pressure at a specific depth. On the basis of geologic history, two fundamental classifications have emerged. If the current effective overburden pressure equals or exceeds the highest pressure to which the soil has been subjected in the past, the soil is classified as normally consolidated. If the current effective overburden pressure is less than the effective overburden pressure that the soil has experienced in the past, the soil is considered to be overconsolidated. The highest historical pressure is referred to as the pre-consolidation pressure [11,12], and the soil's overconsolidation ratio is defined as:

OCR = Overconsolidation ratio

$$OCR = \frac{\text{preconsolidation pressure, } \sigma'_c}{\text{present effective overburden pressure, } \sigma'} \quad (6)$$

Figure 5. Preconsolidation Pressure Determination Graph

The rate of dissipation of a clay layer at a given time t following the application of a load is required in order to estimate the degree of consolidation of the clay layer, and the coefficient of consolidation (C_v) is the parameter that governs the rate of consolidation of the clay layer. Classical differential equation of Terzaghi for the condition of vertical drainage:

$$\frac{\partial(\Delta u)}{\partial t} = C_v \frac{\partial^2(\Delta u)}{\partial z^2} \quad (7)$$

the coefficient of consolidation:

$$C_v = \frac{k}{\gamma_w m_v} \quad (8)$$

At each given point in time, this is another characteristic consolidation parameter that governs the rate of settlement in the field at a certain location.

here,

u = pressure of excess pore

t = time that has passed from the immediate application of a total stress increment.

z = depth from the top of the compressible layer

k = coefficient of permeability

γ_w = unit weight of water

It is important to calculate the value of consolidation coefficient (C_v) in order to apply consolidation theory into practical. Generally speaking, when the liquid limit of the soil increases, the coefficient of consolidation (C_v) decreases. For a given liquid limit of soil, the coefficient of consolidation (C_v) exhibits a large range of variance. Curve-fitting is a process that is used to calculate the value of coefficient of consolidation (C_v) for a specific pressure increase in the oedometer test by comparing the properties of the experimental and theoretical consolidation curves. When time is plotted on a square root or logarithmic scale, the properties of the curves become more apparent.

Square Root of Time Method by Taylor and Logarithm of Time Method by Casagrande are proposed to determine the coefficient of consolidation (C_v).

Logarithm of Time Method

In Casagrande's logarithm of time method, the sample deformation versus log of time plot for a specific incremental loading in the laboratory test is presented in figure 6.

Figure 6. Casagrande's Logarithm of Time Method

In the figure 6 A is the point where portions of the straight line of primary and secondary consolidation intersect. When the ordinate of A is represented by d_{100} , it means that at the end of the primary consolidation process, there is 100% deformation. On the natural scale, the initial curvature of the

deformation versus log t plot is represented by a parabola. On the curved part, choose t_1 and t_2 so that $t_2 = 4t_1$. The difference in deformation of the specimen over time ($t_2 - t_1$) is equal x . The vertical distance $BD = x$ and the deformation related to the horizontal line DE is d_0 (that is, when there is no consolidation, deformation occurs). The deformation at 50% primary consolidation is represented by the ordinate of F point, and the corresponding time (t_{50}) is represented by its abscissa. The time factor (T_v) has a value of 0.197 for average degree consolidation at 50% [11]. So, the coefficient of consolidation is;

$$C_v = \frac{0.197d^2}{t_{50}} \quad (9)$$

The average height of the sample during consolidation is one-half of its typical height for samples that have been drained at both the top and bottom. For samples that have only one side of the sample drained, d equals the average height of the sample during consolidation.

Square Root of Time Method:

In Taylor's square root of time method, for the incremental loading, a plot of deformation versus the square root of time is drawn in figure 7.

Figure 7. Taylor's Square Root of Time Method

In the figure 7 AB line goes through the initial portion of the curve and $\overline{OC} = 1.15 \overline{OB}$ for AC line. Point D represents the intersection of AC line and the consolidation curve, the square root of time for 90% consolidation $\sqrt{t_{90}}$ is given by the abscissa of point D. For 90% consolidation the value of time factor (T_v) is 0.848 [11]. So, the coefficient of consolidation is;

$$C_v = \frac{0.848d^2}{t_{90}} \quad (10)$$

When comparing to the log time technique, which necessitates the proper characterization of the second linear section of the curve far into the secondary compression range, the root time method necessitates compression readings covering a significantly shorter period of time. On the other hand, a straight-line section of the root time plot is not always achieved, and in such circumstances, the log time approach should be employed.

Types of Consolidation

In general soil consolidation settlement is divided into three stages namely immediate settlement or initial consolidation, primary consolidation settlement or consolidation settlement and secondary consolidation settlement or creep settlement. But there is another stage called tertiary consolidation which occurs after secondary consolidation at a higher stress level.

Immediate Settlement

Without any change in moisture content, immediate settlement occurs as a result of elastic deformation of dry soil, as well as moist and saturated soil. The calculation of immediate settlement is usually based on equations derived from elastic theory. Because of their great permeability, clays are able to support the entire added load without generating any immediate settlement. Generally, immediate settlement is usually not important due to the nature of the construction process.

Primary Consolidation Settlement

The expulsion of water from the void spaces causes a volume change in saturated cohesive soils, which results in primary consolidation settlement. There is no primary or secondary “consolidation” settlement when pore water pressure increases in sandy, cohesionless soils, simply immediate settlement due to the high permeability.

Secondary Consolidation Settlement

The plastic adjustment of soil fabric in saturated cohesive soils secondary consolidation settlement is observed. This is also known as creep settlement.

The fundamental principles characterizing the behavior of optimum continuity do not account for the structural rearrangement of materials, which necessitates the development of a fundamental theory that characterizes the mechanical behavior of particle matter and the structural changes that occur in it. The settlement that happens following the completion of primary consolidation is the most obvious manifestation of secondary compression. When it comes to secondary compression, according to [13], the relationship between deformation and the logarithm of time is almost entirely linear. Furthermore, he pointed out that the creeping of clays is an endless process that will never be completed. Data from multiple laboratory tests have been examined, and the results suggest that the secondary settlement may range from less than 10% of the whole settlement to about 100% of the total settlement [14].

Figure 8. Secondary Compression Coefficient Identification

The use of progressive construction on organic soils resulted in an acceleration of consolidation and a reduction in long-term secondary settlement. Furthermore, the surcharging had a considerable impact on the acceleration of secondary settlements, which got around 20% - 30% of the overall settlements that had to be taken into account in the settlement calculations [15]. One-dimensional creep test has a general relationship between the void ratio and the logarithmic time. It is observed at the S-shaped curve in the figure 8 and can be divided into two parts; the main consolidation phase and the secondary consolidation phase [16].

Secondary Compression Causes

Secondary impacts are most likely caused by a variety of mechanisms that vary from soil to soil. Some straightforward techniques are as follows [14]: Large variations in the size of void spaces exist in soils. It is possible in some soils that water will drain from bigger gaps in accordance with primary theory, and then water will more slowly squeeze out of smaller voids, creating a secondary effect. Similarly, in organic soils containing plant matter, water may squeeze out of the voids in accordance with primary theory, and then water may slowly squeeze out of the individual plant cells, through the cell walls, at a slow rate, resulting in the production of a secondary effect. Because of local electrical effects, some clay particles may be surrounded by water, which has been adsorbed onto the surfaces. Water that has been adsorbed may gradually grade outwards into normal liquid water, which may be difficult to detect. In theory, as particles are compressed closer together during primary consolidation, a viscous resistance to volume change should develop, which could result in the appearance of apparent secondary effects. A shallow highly compressible soil and a deeper less compressible soil are involved in some case histories of settlement of extensive embankments. Rather than being caused by apparent secondary settlement, it may be caused by delayed primary consolidation of the comparatively incompressible soil, which cannot drain until the overlying, more compressible soil layers have begun to consolidate. If you have an organic soil that is consolidating under a certain load, you may notice that the hydraulic conductivity of the soil drops by more than an order of magnitude. Consolidation occurs naturally at a faster rate in the beginning, but then at a slower rate as a result of the loss in hydraulic conductivity, resulting in an apparent secondary influence on the environment. It is possible for very nonlinear stress-strain curves to result in a settlement-time behavior that appears to be a combination of primary consolidation and secondary consolidation. The secondary consolidation coefficient is defined as the slope of the void ratio versus logarithmic time in the secondary consolidation stage [16]:

$$C_{\alpha} = -\frac{\Delta e}{\Delta \log t} \quad (11)$$

In order to calculate the secondary consolidation settlement [17]:

$$S_s = \frac{C_{\alpha}}{1+e_p} H_0 (\Delta \log t) \quad (12)$$

C_{α} = Index of secondary consolidation

H_0 = Compressible layer's thickness

e_p = Void ratio at the end of primary consolidation

$$\Delta \log t = \frac{t_{sc}}{t_p} \quad (13)$$

t_{sc} is the time when secondary consolidation calculations are done, and t_p is the time when secondary consolidation starts.

$$\text{Index of modified secondary consolidation} = \frac{C_{\alpha}}{1+e_p}$$

After conducting long-term (140-day) creep tests [18] on Batiscan clay under various vertical stresses, it was discovered that the strain-time behavior was often nonlinear, as indicated in the Figure 9. The following conclusions were drawn from these findings:

Type I soil is one that has been overconsolidated, in which the vertical stress is less than the preconsolidation stress and there is no substantial cross-point between the primary and secondary consolidation.

Type II soil is one that has been normally consolidated, in which the vertical consolidation pressure is somewhat near to the preconsolidation stress and during secondary compression, the slope of $\sigma_v - \log t$ is substantially greater than during Type I compression.

Type III soil is one that has been normally consolidated, in which the vertical consolidation pressure is greater than the preconsolidation pressure and the slope of $\sigma_v - \log t$ is steadily decreased.

Figure 9. Types of Relationships between Strain and Time

Secondary compression coefficient (C_{α}) is a parameter that describes the creep characteristics of clay when tested in one dimension. According to previous research, the secondary compression coefficient (C_{α}) is affected by the types of soil, the consolidation stress, the overconsolidation, the length of the stress, the shear stress, and the temperature.

Types of soil:

Secondary consolidation can be defined as the technique of continuing the volume change that is began by primary consolidation and that is then continued by secondary consolidation. Among the effects of this process are the deformation of individual particles as well as the relative movements of individual particles in relation to one another. Because of this, the rate of secondary consolidation in typically consolidated clays with relatively high contact stresses will be larger than the rate of secondary consolidation in overconsolidated soils with relatively low contact stresses. The compressibility of pure clays under external load was found to be dependent not only on the negative charges and crystallite structure of clay minerals, but also on the ion concentration, cation valency, dielectric constant, and temperature of the pore fluid in which the clay minerals were found to be present [19].

Dependence of stress:

It is unclear what the relationship is between the rate of secondary consolidation and the stress associated with consolidation. Neither secondary consolidation settlement nor consolidation stress were found to be related in Haefeli's study [20], nor were secondary compression index (C_{α}) and

consolidation stress found to be related in Newland's study [21], nor did secondary compression index (C_{α}) decrease with stress in either study [22]. The amount of strain was independent of the amount of consolidation stress, rose significantly with the amount of consolidation stress, and increased with the magnitude of the load.

The secondary compression index (C_{α}) of typically consolidated clays decreased as the consolidation stress was increased. For natural undisturbed soil, the secondary compression index (C_{α}) grew progressively as the value of σ'_z was increased. Vertical stress was found to be connected with a secondary compression index (C_{α}) [18]. Increasing the value of σ'_z led to an increase in the secondary compression index (C_{α}). With a rise in effective stress, the secondary compression index (C_{α}) drops in value (or strength). Series of one-dimensional consolidation tests were conducted on Sabkha soil, with the results revealing a strong relationship between the secondary compression index (C_{α}) and effective stress [23].

The preconsolidation pressure was shown to be related to the secondary compression index (C_{α}). For the bentonite under investigation, a vertical pressure rise was shown to be more successful in lowering the water content and the void ratio. Volume change behavior of clays caused by an increase in vertical pressure is significantly influenced by mineralogy, physicochemical interactions between clay particles and the pore fluid, and pore fluid physicochemical interactions with clay particles [24]. The secondary compression coefficient reduced as the amount of stress grew, but it increased when the amount of plasticity index increased [25].

Dependence of time:

Long-term odometer experiments on Middleton peat revealed that creep makes a significant contribution to total settlement, as seen by the results [26]. According to the findings of this study, the secondary compression index did not remain constant over time but rather increased with time under continuous effective stress. The secondary compression index may remain constant over time, or it may drop or rise over time.

Shear Stress:

When comparing one - dimensional (1D) compression to three - dimensional (3D) compression, it is shown that secondary consolidation happens more frequently in one-dimensional compression.

Temperature:

Increased testing temperature decreased the strength of the bonds at the sites of contact, which resulted in a decrease in the compressibility of the material. The coefficient of secondary consolidation for specimens that were routinely consolidated as well as specimens that were over consolidated was not affected by the testing temperature. Because of the increase in temperature, the secondary compression curve becomes steeper. The coefficient of secondary compression proved to be an extremely effective instrument in explaining secondary consolidation [23]

Tertiary Consolidation

Clayey soils are composed of two major components: one is fabric, which describes the geometrical arrangement of mineral particles and void spaces, and another one is particle interactions, which describes the bonding mechanism and nature of shear resistance. Creep deformation is responsible for the changes in both components.

According to Buisman's remark, the creeping of clays never terminates, which was at first highly questioned not only by Terzaghi but also by others around the world [13]. In the meantime, this notion has been accepted and verified by test findings that reveal long-term creep, as well as the transition to tertiary creep in some instances [27].

Tertiary compression is defined as the vertical portion of the strain-log t curve at lower stress levels. Despite the fact that tertiary compression changes at a rising rate, it relates to a decrease in the rate at which the strain is applied. Figure 10 shows that secondary creep should be regarded as a transition zone between primary and tertiary creep, with the tertiary creep eventually leading to cracking [28]. Creep rupture is a type of failure that occurs at the end of the tertiary creep cycle of a material. This is mainly due to the restructuring of soil particles, which has occurred. The primary

creep is always present, while the tertiary creep is only noticed for stress levels close to the pressure of failure, and the secondary creep is only observed in rare instances.

Figure 10. Primary, Secondary and Tertiary Creep Definition

Comparing the findings of six one-dimensional tests with data acquired on the in-situ consolidation behavior of blue clay allowed us to determine the secondary and tertiary compressibility properties of Samson Blue Clay, which were then compared to one another. Aside from that, the soft clay microfibrer structures were examined at the continuous stage, as well as at the primary, secondary, and tertiary compression stages. According to the researchers, the observed in-situ secondary and tertiary compression ratios were around 2 to 4 times higher than those measured in the laboratory, and that the third compression was caused by the fragmentation of organic matter as a result of long-term compression [29]. When it comes to the compression of peat, primary consolidation was the most important factor, however consolidation happens in a very short period of time when compared to clay. Despite the fact that secondary compression is less significant in amplitude than primary consolidation, it has the potential to be quite important in terms of the design life of a structure. In the test findings, it was discovered that there was tertiary compression, which may not be very relevant in terms of the design life of the structure.

Stabilization of the soil was achieved through the use of ordinary Portland cement, Slag from a blast furnace, and siliceous sand. Increases in the rate of tertiary compression for untreated peats occurred as the consolidation pressure increased, showing that the tertiary component of the soils fused with the secondary component when high consolidation pressure was encountered. Four peat samples with a wide variety of fiber compositions were exposed to one-dimensional consolidation experiments in order to investigate the consolidation behavior of peats [30].

There was a suggestion of a two-level structure including macro-pores and micro-pores in tertiary compression, and this was characterized as the time at which the rate of secondary compression rose with the logarithm of time. The void ratio was the most important factor influencing the rate of tertiary compression, with peat type being the second most important factor. In the majority of cases, the tertiary compression component was greater than the secondary compression component, and it declined as the load increment ratio increased. The influence of the tertiary component was significant for smaller load increment ratios, and for load increment ratios less than one, the tertiary component accounted for 35%-45% of the overall load [19].

Settlement Comparison: Predicted and Observed

Using back-analyzed parameters, excellent agreement was achieved in terms of the expected rate and quantity of settlements, respectively [31,32]. Using laboratory and field studies, it was determined that the measured settlements fell within a reasonable range. Furthermore, it was discovered that measured and computed settlements followed settlement rates that were very close [33].

The calculated settlement results were quite close to the observed settlement outcomes, which was unexpected [34]. They used prefabricated vertical drains in soft Bangkok clay and came to the conclusion that the degree of consolidation calculated from the pore-pressure dissipation measurements coincided with the degree of consolidation estimated from the settlement measurements [35]. With prefabricated vertical drains, the long-term performance of a wide embankment on soft clay was enhanced, and the projected pore-water pressure was found to be in reasonable agreement with the measured values [36]. The accuracy of the estimation of hydraulic conductivity of soils improved as a result of the installation of vertical drains; field observations were found to be quite near to the analytical calculations [37].

There was a considerable difference in the rate of settlement between the calculated and measured values, and the predicted settlement amounts were determined to be reliable and equivalent to the field measurements [31,38]. Settlement measurements were taken, and it was determined that the estimated settlement matched the observed settlement [39]. On the other hand, the time required to complete the settlement in the field was less than anticipated. A study on the enhancement of soft clay by vacuum preloading was given by [40]. It was discovered in their research that there was a high degree of concordance between the estimated and forecasted settlements. Furthermore, the ratio of $C_{h(\text{field})}$ to $C_{h(\text{lab})}$ was found to be 2 in that study.

Using field measurements, Cao was able to perform back-calculations of consolidation parameters, and they discovered that the compression index was generally greater than what had been measured in the laboratory, and that the coefficient of consolidation back-calculated was greater than the values calculated from pore pressure measurement [41]. Following an evaluation of the field performance of embankments on soft clay deposits with and without PVD (prefabricated vertical drain) improvement, it was determined that the settlement quantity and rate of measured values were more than the calculated values [42]. Reverse analyses were carried out on the compressibility parameters of PVD improved soft ground in Southern Vietnam. The back calculated values of consolidation coefficient (C_h) were approximately 4 to 6 times greater than the average coefficient of consolidation values (C_v) obtained from conventional oedometer tests, and the secondary compression ratios (C_α) were approximately 1.5 times greater than those obtained from laboratory tests [43].

Here,

C_v = Vertical Coefficient of Consolidation

C_h = Horizontal Coefficient of Consolidation

This is the rate at which a ground area settles when prefabricated vertical drains are used in its construction. The results of two documented case studies led him to the conclusion that estimated coefficients of radial consolidation were higher than the values obtained from oedometer tests in both cases, and that coefficients of consolidation (C_v) obtained from field tests were very close to the results of standard oedometer tests in both of the cases [44].

[45] made a comparison between the preliminary consolidation parameters and the final consolidation parameters obtained from the pilot test embankment after the soil enhancement project was complete. According to the results of the back study, the horizontal and vertical consolidation coefficients for coastal clay are both 1.5. Aside from that, the settlements' sphere of impact was overstated in another way. Compared to predictions, the theoretical consolidation settlements determined from laboratory test findings were significantly greater [46]. The back-analyzed coefficient of consolidation of the clay was higher, whereas the compression ratio was lower, than the initial design estimate, indicating that the design was correct [47].

Soil Profiling and Property Estimation

A physical evaluation of the soil, as well as an estimation of its mechanical and chemical qualities, must be completed prior to any analysis work being undertaken. It is common practice to divide the compressible layer into sublayers with heights $h_1, h_2, h_3, \dots, h_n$. Effective overburden stress, induced stress increment due to an external impact, and compressibility constants are all calculated for each layer on an average representative basis. For a homogeneous soil deposit, obtaining the relevant sample from the field and carrying out appropriate experiments in the laboratory can be used to reasonably anticipate the settlement behavior of the underlain layer. However, in the case of non-homogeneous soil deposits, such as those containing erratic or lenticular deposits of sand, silt, or soft clay, the conventional method of soil profiling with a limited number of boreholes may frequently fail to provide critical information about weak pockets of compressible layers, resulting in the need for additional investigation. In some cases, if the penetrometer data are properly calibrated, the information obtained from the measurements can be sufficient to estimate soil qualities such as physical state, strength parameters, and deformation characteristics, among others. In soil classification, stratigraphy, and variability determination, the cone penetrometer has been in use for more than 50 years. Since its inception as a mechanical cone, it has progressed to include an electric cone and a piezocone, both of which are now employed to conduct in-field testing. Electric cones are capable of monitoring tip resistance and skin resistance on a continual basis in a closed circuit. It is possible to measure pore pressure at various locations depending on the location of the piezometric elements in the filter element.

Analysis of Settlement

The implications of the typical approach of splitting soft ground into one or more layers in order to calculate consolidation settlement of soft ground are examined in detail. Using numerical analysis to determine the accuracy of the calculation and the settlement behavior caused by layering, this study discovered that the existing settlement calculation method consistently underestimates settlement, and that the smaller number of dividing layers used, the smaller amount of calculated settlement was seen. Furthermore, when the ground is divided into an unbounded number of layers, the settlement is 1.2 to 50 times greater than when the ground is considered as a single layer, and the difference gets bigger at lower ratios of applied pressure to effective stress (A_0), higher ratios of layer thickness to footing width (H/B), and lower ratios of the length to width of a footing (L/B). Even when utilizing the existing settlement calculation method, it is possible to acquire the precise settlement under a single-layer scenario if the typical depth of calculation of the effective stress is chosen at a depth of around 10% to 38% below the top of the clay layer.

It is explained in detail in the project's description that the numerical analysis of the consolidation behavior of an experimental test trial embankment constructed on a soft soil base is being carried out in this study. The geological profile, field apparatus, laboratory test findings, and derivation of soil parameters for numerical modeling are all discussed in detail. In accordance with Biot's consolidation theory, one-dimensional consolidation analysis and nonlinear finite-element analysis are used to estimate the settling of an embankment structure. The findings of the finite element analysis are calibrated against the recorded field data collected over a period of more than three years. Through the use of a parametric research, the development and absorption of excess pore water pressure, long-term settlement, and horizontal displacement are anticipated and analyzed in the context of the sensitivity of embankment performance to some essential elements.

In terms of the stress dependency of consolidation parameters, the settlement computer programs indicate that the link between the coefficient of consolidation and the stress may be determined just by the input parameters. This study describes a method in which both stress and permeability are expressed as functions of strain in the form of a power law.

Identification of the parameters for consolidation settlement according to multi objective optimization, consolidation settling is usually difficult to foresee owing to the difficulty of natural ground conditions, which makes it difficult to predict. This study presents a back analysis approach for consolidation settlement that is based on Pareto multi objective optimization. Flow and displacement models for unsaturated soil foundations are developed in the collaborative Multiphysics software environment, which allows for easy interaction with the model. To identify soil parameters based on various of

different sorts of measurements, a multi-objective optimization technique is used. The proposed back analysis method is demonstrated through the use of a case study involving a highway trial embankment. Using the measured displacement and pore water pressures, it is possible to estimate the mechanical and hydraulic properties of the soil at the same time. The results reveal that the bi-objective Pareto front has a crisp rectangular pattern in its pattern. Only displacement is utilized in back analysis when the numerical model with optimal soil parameters is used, and vice versa when the numerical model with optimum soil parameters is used when only displacement is used in back analysis. The soil parameters of the reasonable compromise obtained from bi-objective back analysis, on the other hand, can be reasonably simulated for both displacement and porewater pressure, and can also be reasonably predicted for settlement.

PARAMETRIC ANALYSIS

Introduction

GeoStru brings together a talented group of professionals with extensive experience and expertise in a variety of fields, including geotechnical engineering, structural engineering, geophysics, geology, topography, geomechanics, hydrology, soil testing, and other related areas of expertise. This software has made it easier and more reliable to analyze soil parameters such as settlement, bearing capacity, and the effect of increasing the load on the foundation.

Data Collection

All the field works and field tests were conducted as per standard procedure as laid down in ASTM specification are as follows. Figure 11 shows the data collection procedure from the field.

Figure 11. Data Collection Procedure from the Field

Extraction of Disturbed Soil Sample

Soil sample in the disturbed state have been extracted from the each 0.91m and 1.52m depth of each boring using split spoon sampler in accordance with ASTM D1586 standard procedure. These soil samples after extraction, have duly been classified in situ, in order to reconstruct a depth wise stratification chart of the each bore hole.

Extraction of Undisturbed Soil Sample

As both of the physical and the engineering properties of the soil are greatly affected by the disturbance of the soil sample, soil sample in the undisturbed state are generally preferred in collection in order to perform certain laboratory tests which eventually help to evaluate the bearing capacities as well as Geotechnical observations. Undisturbed soils are collected from cohesive strata. Samples of cohesive soils were obtained with a three inch thin-walled (Shelby) tube sampler in general accordance with ASTM D1587.

Execution of Standard Penetration Test

Standard penetration tests were executed at each 1.5m interval in all the bore holes with the simultaneous collection of the disturbed soil samples. The tests were executed by using a split spoon sampler of 50mm outer diameter and 37.5mm inner diameter attached to the lower end of the drilling rod. 63.5 kg automatic hammer was allowed to fall freely from a height of 760mm. The blows of the automatic hammer drove the spoon into the soil up to 450mm. The number of blows required for last 300mm of penetration of the spoon was entered into the bore chart as being the ASTM standard penetration test results.

Recording of Ground Water Table

After completing the field investigations, the level of ground water in each of the bore hole has been recorded by a measuring tape and found within a variable depth measured from the existing level of the ground. These are apparent level of ground water formed by the entrapped surface water.

Laboratory Tests

The following laboratory tests have been conducted on disturbed and undisturbed samples in the laboratory:

1. Grain Size Analysis (Mechanical)
2. Grain Size Analysis (Hydrometer)
3. Moisture Content
4. Specific Gravity
5. Unconfined Compression Test
6. Atterberg Limit
7. Direct Shear Test

Study Area

There are three locations for this thesis. Bangladesh has been divided into four Seismic Zones namely Zone-1, Zone-2, Zone-3 and Zone-4 with values of Seismic Zoning coefficient, z of 0.12, 0.20, 0.28 and 0.36 respectively. According to the zoning map, location-1 falls in the Zone-4, location-2 falls in the Zone-2, and location-3 falls in the Zone-3. Figure 12 shows the Seismic zoning map of Bangladesh.

Location 1

Construction of proposed four storied residential building on khatian No. S. A.- 508, B. R. S.- 1217, J. L. No. S. A.- 157, R. S.- 48, Mouza- Trishal, Word No.- 05, Village- Trishal, District- Mymensingh, Bangladesh. Figure 13 shows the bore hole location of this project.

Location 2

Construction of proposed seven storied residential building at khatian No.- C. S.- 99, S. A.- 221, R. S.- 64, Mouza- Kunia, District- Gazipur, Bangladesh. Figure 14 shows the bore hole location of this project.

Location 3

Construction of proposed four storied school building at khatian No.- 83, Mouza- Koira Dori Para, District- Sirajganj, Bangladesh. Figure 15 shows the bore hole location of this project.

Figure 12. Seismic zoning map of Bangladesh
Source: BNBC-2020, Part-6, Chapter-2

Figure 13. Location 1

Figure 14. Location 2

Figure 15. Location 3

Software Modelling

Figure 16 shows the flow chart of software modelling.

Data Entry

Soil Parameters

At first, fixed the soil parameter as shown in table 1.

Table 1. Soil Parameters

Soil Type	Gamma (KN/m ³)	Angle of Shearing resistance (°)	Cohesion (KN/m ²)	Elastic Modulus (KN/m ²)	Oedometric modulus (KN/m ²)	Poisson ratio
Clay	19.613	22	9.807	0	4903.325	0.5
Silt	17.652	28	0	7354.98	0	0.35
Sand	18.63	33	0	19613.3	0	0.3
Gravel	19.613	36	0	49033.25	0	0.256
Rock	22.55	45	0	98066.5	0	0.15

Footing Parameters

In the foundation system data tab footing parameters were given, example is given in figure 17.

Figure 16. Flow Chart of Software Modelling

The screenshot shows a software interface for defining footing parameters. At the top, a diagram illustrates a footing cross-section with various parameters labeled: EL (Terrain extension on the left), ER (Terrain extension on the right), IS (Slope inclination), DS (Foundation distance from slope), BL (Foundation base, left), BR (Foundation base, right), Hs (Column height), Hi (Footing height), Ip (Inclination of bearing surface), B (Foundation width), D (Bearing surface depth), and HF (Embedded height). Below the diagram is a 'Beam foundation' section with the following parameters:

- Foundation type: Strip footing
- Foundation length: L = 3 [m]
- Foundation width: B = 3 [m]
- Foundation base, right: BR = 1.2 [m]
- Foundation base, left: BL = 1.2 [m]
- Footing height: HI = 0.6 [m]
- Column height: HS = 3 [m]
- Bearing surface depth: D = 2.59 [m]
- Embedded height: HF = 2.59 [m]
- Inclination of bearing surface: IP = 0 [°]

There is also a 'Subgrade' section with 'Shoulder, Height' set to 0 [m]. The 'Soil profile and GWT' section includes:

- Terrain extension on the left: EL = 4 [m]
- Terrain extension on the right: ER = 4 [m]
- Slope inclination: IS = 0 [°]
- Foundation distance from slope: DS = 0 [m]
- GWT depth from ground surf.: 0 [m]

Figure 17. Footing Parameters

Soil stratigraphy

Then soil stratigraphy from the soil report was created in Microsoft excel. It was very convenient to work with MS excel sheet, an example is given in table 3-2.

Table 2. Soil Stratigraphy

SL No.	Soil Layer	Depth (m)	Layer Thickness (m)
1	Medium stiff clay	0 – 2.44	2.44
2	Medium loose sand	2.44 – 6.71	5.48
3	Clayey silt	6.71 – 11.58	4.89
4	Stiff clay	11.58 – 14.32	2.74
5	High plastic clay	14.32 – 19.82	4.27

After that inputted the value in the software, shows in figure 18.

Figure 18. Soil Stratigraphy in Software

After that borehole was created by “Geostru” software fixing the soil parameters and soil stratigraphy. And then we calculated the consolidation settlement for different parameter. Normal stress was applied at different range obtained from field. Figure 19 shows an example of a borehole.

Figure 19. Borehole Example

And then calculated the consolidation settlement with software. The software gave value at once. It was also possible to change any parameter like size, shape, stress, length, width very easily.

Data Analysis

Data analysis was computed by GeoStru and Microsoft excel. The graph was drawn by the origin from there we calculated intercept, coefficient of correlation, degree of relationship, slope and level of significance(p-value). An example is given in figure 21. Figure 20 shows the pressure bulbs for 100 kN/m² normal stress and consider 50% foundation length.

Figure 20. Pressure Bulbs

Figure 21. Settlement Curve

CASE STUDY: ANALYSIS IN DIFFERENT LOCATIONS OF BANGLADESH

The primary and secondary consolidation settlement were calculated for different values of normal stress, footing size and layer thickness. But in general, this study considered a strip footing of (3m × 3m) size and 500 kN/m² normal stress for the analysis purpose. This study assumed bearing surface depth and embedded height is 2.59 m which was recommended in soil report.

Soil Stratigraphy

In this study six boreholes in three different locations of Bangladesh are considered. Soil stratigraphy figure of different borehole in different location are shown in figure 22-25. Table 3-8 show the soil stratigraphy table in different locations.

Figure 22. Location 1 (a) Borehole 1 (LB-11) (b) Borehole 2 (LB-12)

Table 3. Soil Stratigraphy (LB – 11)

Soil Layer	Depth (m)	Layer Thickness (m)
Sand	0 – 2.43	2.43
Medium stiff silt	2.43 – 4.27	1.82
Medium stiff silt	4.27 – 10.06	5.79
High plastic clay	10.06 – 15.55	5.48

Table 4. Soil Stratigraphy (LB – 12)

Soil Layer	Depth (m)	Layer Thickness (m)
Sand	0 – 2.44	2.44
Silt with some clay	2.44 – 6.71	4.27
Silt with some clay	6.71 – 9.75	3.05
High plastic clay	9.75 – 15.54	5.79

Figure 23. Location 2 (a) Borehole 1 (LB-21) (b)Borehole 2 (LB-22)

Table 5. Soil Stratigraphy (LB – 21)

No. of Layer	Soil Layer	Depth (m)	Layer Thickness (m)
1	Medium stiff clay	0 – 2.44	2.44
2	Medium loose sand	2.44 – 6.71	5.48
3	Clayey silt	6.71 – 11.58	4.89
4	Stiff clay	11.58 – 14.32	2.74
5	High plastic clay	14.32 – 19.82	4.27

Table 6. Soil Stratigraphy (LB22)

Soil Layer	Depth (m)	Layer Thickness (m)
Light brown clay	0 – 2.44	2.44
Medium loose sand	2.44 – 7.94	5.47
Clayey silt	7.94 – 11.28	3.35
Stiff plastic clay	11.28 – 14.63	3.35
Light brown clay	14.63 – 18.59	3.96

Figure 24. Borehole 3 Borehole 1 (LB-31)

Figure 25. Borehole 3 Borehole 2 (LB-32)

Table 7. Soil Stratigraphy (LB – 31)

Soil Layer	Depth (m)	Layer Thickness (m)
Fine sand	0 – 3.9624	3.9624
Clayey silt	3.9624 – 5.4864	1.524
Gray clayey silt	5.4864 – 7.0104	3.048
Clayey silt	7.0104 – 10.0584	3.048
Fine sand	10.0584 – 14.6304	4.572
Light gray clay	14.6304 – 17.6784	3.048
Light gray clay	17.6784 – 20.7264	3.048

Table 8. Soil Stratigraphy (LB32)

Soil Layer	Depth (m)	Layer Thickness (m)
Fine sand	0 – 3.9624	3.96
Clayey silt	3.9624 – 8.2296	4.2672
Gray clay	8.2296 – 10.0584	1.8288

Fine sand	10.0584 – 14.6304	4.572
Brown clay	14.6304 – 18.8976	4.2672
Light gray clay	18.8976 – 20.7264	1.8288

Change in Consolidation Settlement due to Change in Normal Stress

The table 9-14 shows different consolidation settlement values due to change in normal stress in different types of location of Bangladesh.

Table 9. Settlement Values for Different Normal Stress (LB-11)

Normal Stress (KN/m ²)	Primary Consolidation Settlement (cm)	Secondary Consolidation Settlement in 10 Years (cm)
100	0.24	2.19
300	1.16	2.19
500	2.1	2.18
800	3.57	2.18
1000	4.59	2.17
1500	7.24	2.16

Table 10. Settlement Values for Different Normal Stress (LB-12)

Normal Stress (KN/m ²)	Primary Consolidation Settlement (cm)	Secondary Consolidation Settlement in 10 Years (cm)
100	0.26	2.31
300	1.25	2.31
500	2.28	2.31
800	3.87	2.3
1000	4.97	2.3
1500	7.85	2.28

The figure 26 shows the graph for consolidation settlement vs normal stress at Location 1, borehole 1. The figure 27 shows the graph for normal stress vs consolidation settlement at Location 1, borehole 2.

Figure 26. Settlement Vs Normal stress (LB-11)

Figure 27. Settlement Vs Normal stress (LB-12)

Table 11. Settlement Values for Different Normal Stress (LB-21)

Normal Stress (KN/m ²)	Primary Consolidation Settlement, Layer- 4 (cm)	Secondary Consolidation Settlement in 10 Years, Layer- 4 (cm)	Primary Consolidation Settlement, Layer- 5 (cm)	Secondary Consolidation Settlement in 10 Years, Layer- 5 (cm)
100	0.05	0.55	0.08	0
300	0.27	0.55	0.41	0
500	0.5	0.55	0.73	0
800	0.85	0.55	1.23	0
1000	1.09	0.55	1.57	0
1500	1.7	0.54	2.43	0

Table 12. Settlement Values for Different Normal Stress (LB-22)

Normal Stress (KN/m ²)	Primary Consolidation Settlement, Layer- 3 (cm)	Primary Consolidation Settlement, Layer- 4 (cm)
100	0.29	0.09
300	1.48	0.42
500	2.76	0.77
800	4.85	1.32
1000	6.33	1.69
1500	10.35	2.66

The figure 28 shows the graph for normal stress vs consolidation settlement at Location 2, borehole 1. The figure 29 shows the graph for normal stress vs consolidation settlement at Location 2, borehole 2.

Figure 28. Settlement Vs Normal Stress (LB-21)

Figure 29. Settlement Vs Normal Stress (LB-22)

Table 13. Settlement Values for Different Normal Stress (LB-31)

Normal Stress (KN/m ²)	Primary Consolidation Settlement, Layer- 2 (cm)	Primary Consolidation Settlement, Layer- 3 (cm)
100	0.99	0.45
300	6.24	2.45
500	13.07	4.9
800	25.2	9.2
1000	34.19	12.4

Table 14. Settlement Values for Different Normal Stress (LB-32)

Normal Stress (KN/m ²)	Primary Consolidation Settlement, Layer-2 (cm)	Primary Consolidation Settlement, Layer-3 (cm)
100	1.34	0.19
300	7.44	0.93
500	14.96	1.73
800	28.2	3.05
1000	38.06	4

The figure 30 shows the graph for normal stress vs consolidation settlement at Location 3, borehole 1. The figure 31 shows the graph for normal stress vs consolidation settlement at Location 3, borehole 2.

Figure 30. Settlement Vs Normal Stress (LB-31)

Figure 31. Settlement Vs Normal Stress (LB-32)

Here analyzed the result obtained from applying normal stress 100 KN/m² to 1000 KN/m² to a strip footing of 3m × 3m to observe the different value of consolidation settlement. The statistical analysis is given in table 15 which shows the values of standard deviation, mean, intercept and slope.

Table 15. Consolidation Settlement Values for Different Normal Stress

Normal Stress (KN/m ²)	L1B1	L1B2	L2B1	L2B2	L3B1	L3B2	Mean	Standard Deviation
100	0.24	0.26	0.05	0.09	0.45	0.19	0.21	0.142
300	1.16	1.25	0.27	0.42	2.45	0.93	1.08	0.778
500	2.1	2.28	0.5	0.77	4.6	1.73	2.05	1.570
800	3.57	3.87	0.85	1.32	9.2	3.05	3.64	2.983
1000	4.59	4.97	1.09	1.69	12.4	4	4.79	4.047
Intercept	-0.278	-0.303	-0.073	-0.106	-1.341	-0.311	-0.40	
Slope	0.004	0.0052	0.0012	0.0018	0.0134	0.0042	0.005	

The following table describe the values of consolidation settlement in centimeters for different values of applied normal stress in KN/m². The maximum consolidation value was observed 12.4 cm at 1000 KN/m² and minimum consolidation value was observed 0.09 cm at 100 KN/m² stress. The slope is 0.005 cm and negative intercept value was found.

Secondary Consolidation Settlement in Number of Years

The table 16-21 shows secondary consolidation settlement for number of years in different types of location of Bangladesh.

Table 16. Secondary Consolidation Settlement for Number of Years (LB-11)

Normal Stress (KN/m ²)	Years	Secondary Consolidation Settlement (cm)
500	1	0
500	2	0.66
500	4	1.33
500	5	1.53
500	7	1.85
500	10	2.18
500	15	2.57

Table 17. Secondary Consolidation Settlement in Number of Years (LB-12)

Normal Stress (KN/m ²)	Years	Secondary Consolidation Settlement (cm)
500	1	0
500	2	0.69
500	4	1.39
500	5	1.61
500	7	1.95
500	10	2.31
500	15	2.71

The figure 32 shows the graph for secondary consolidation settlement vs number of years at Location 1, borehole 1. The figure 33 shows the graph for secondary consolidation settlement vs years at Location 1, borehole 2.

Figure 32. Secondary Consolidation Settlement Vs Number of Years

Figure 33. Secondary Consolidation Settlement Vs Number of Years (LB-12)

Table 18. Secondary Consolidation Settlement (LB-21)

Years	Secondary Consolidation Settlement, Layer- 4 (cm)	Secondary Consolidation Settlement, Layer- 5 (cm)
1	2.53	0
2	3.3	0.16
4	4.06	0.33

5	4.31	0.38
7	4.68	0.46
10	5.07	0.55
15	5.52	0.64

Table 19. Secondary Consolidation Settlement (LB-22)

Years	Secondary Consolidation Settlement, Layer- 3 (cm)	Secondary Consolidation Settlement, Layer- 4 (cm)
1	0	0
2	0.5	0.2
4	1	0.4
5	1.16	0.47
7	1.4	0.56
10	1.66	0.67
15	1.95	0.79

The figure 34 shows the graph for secondary consolidation settlement vs years at Location 2, borehole 1. The figure 35 shows the graph for secondary consolidation settlement vs years at Location 2, borehole 2.

Figure 34. Secondary Settlement Vs Number of Years (LB-21)

Figure 35. Secondary settlement Vs Number of Years (LB-22)

Table 20. Secondary Consolidation Settlement (LB-31)

Years	Secondary Consolidation Settlement, Layer- 2 (cm)	Secondary Consolidation Settlement, Layer- 3 (cm)
1	0	0
2	0.21	0.18
4	0.42	0.36
5	0.49	0.41
7	0.59	0.5
10	0.7	0.6

Table 21. Secondary Consolidation Settlement (LB-32)

Years	Secondary Consolidation Settlement, Layer- 2 (cm)	Secondary Consolidation Settlement, Layer- 3 (cm)
1	0	0
2	0.62	0.22

4	1.24	0.44
5	1.44	0.51
7	1.74	0.61
10	2.06	0.73

The figure 36 shows the graph for secondary consolidation settlement vs years at Location 3, borehole 1. The figure 37 shows the graph for secondary consolidation settlement vs years at Location 3, borehole 2.

Figure 36. Secondary settlement Vs Number of years (LB-31)

Figure 37. Secondary consolidation settlement Vs Number of years (LB-32)

Secondary consolidation settlement was calculated using Terzaghi logarithmic method. We have analyzed the result of secondary consolidation settlement in 2 to 10 years and observe the different value of consolidation settlement. The statistical analysis is given in table 22 which shows the values of standard deviation, mean, intercept and slope.

Table 22. Secondary Consolidation Settlement Values

Number of Years	L1B1	L1B2	L2B1	L2B2	L3B1	L3B2	Mean	Standard Deviation
2	0.66	0.69	3.3	0.5	0.21	0.62	1.00	1.142
4	1.33	1.39	4.06	1	0.42	1.24	1.57	1.269
5	1.53	1.61	4.31	1.16	0.49	1.44	1.76	1.316
7	1.85	1.95	4.68	1.4	0.59	1.74	2.04	1.387
10	2.18	2.31	5.07	1.66	0.7	2.06	2.33	1.464
Intercept	0.492	0.503	3.095	0.366	0.153	0.454	0.844	
Slope	0.182	0.194	0.212	0.139	0.059	0.173	0.160	

The following table describe the values of secondary consolidation settlement in centimeters for 2 to 10 years. The maximum consolidation value was observed 5.07 cm at 10 years and minimum consolidation value was observed 0.66 cm at 2nd year. The slope is 0.160 cm and positive intercept value was found.

Difference Between Settlement at Corner and Center of the Foundation

The table 23-28 shows consolidation settlement values at center and corner in different types of location of Bangladesh

Table 23. Consolidation Settlement at Center and Corner (LB-11)

Normal Stress (KN/m ²)	Primary Consolidation Settlement at Center (cm)	Primary Consolidation Settlement at Corner (cm)
100	0.24	0.23
300	1.16	1.1
500	2.1	2
800	3.57	3.39
1000	4.59	4.35
1500	7.24	6.85

Table 24. Consolidation Settlement at Center and Corner (LB-12)

Normal Stress (KN/m ²)	Primary Consolidation Settlement at Center (cm)	Primary Consolidation Settlement at Corner (cm)
100	0.26	0.25
300	1.25	1.19
500	2.28	2.16
800	3.87	3.67
1000	4.97	4.71
1500	7.85	7.42

The figure 38 shows the graph for settlement difference between corner and center at Location 1, borehole 1. The figure 39 shows the graph for settlement difference between corner and center at Location 1, borehole 2.

Figure 38. Settlement vs Normal Stress at Center and Corner (LB-11)

Figure 39. Settlement Vs Normal Stress (LB-12)

Table 25. Consolidation Settlement at Center and Corner (LB-21)

Normal Stress (KN/m ²)	Primary Consolidation Settlement at Center, Layer- 4 (cm)	Primary Consolidation Settlement at Corner, Layer- 4 (cm)	Primary Consolidation Settlement at Center, Layer- 5 (cm)	Primary Consolidation Settlement at Corner, Layer- 5 (cm)
100	0.05	0.05	0.08	0.08
300	0.27	0.26	0.41	0.4
500	0.5	0.48	0.73	0.72
800	0.85	0.81	1.23	1.2

1000	1.09	1.04	1.57	1.53
1500	1.7	1.63	2.43	2.37

Table 26. Consolidation Settlement at Center and Corner (LB-22)

Normal Stress (KN/m ²)	Primary Consolidation Settlement at Center, Layer- 3 (cm)	Primary Consolidation Settlement at Corner, Layer- 3 (cm)	Primary Consolidation Settlement at Center, Layer- 4 (cm)	Primary Consolidation Settlement at Corner, Layer- 4 (cm)
100	0.29	0.26	0.09	0.08
300	1.48	1.33	0.42	0.4
500	2.76	2.48	0.77	0.74
800	4.88	4.34	1.32	1.25
1000	6.33	5.66	1.69	1.6
1500	10.35	9.21	2.66	2.52

The figure 40 shows the graph for settlement difference between corner and center at Location 2, borehole 1. The figure 41 shows the graph for settlement difference between corner and center at Location 2, borehole 2.

Figure 40. Settlement Vs Normal Stress (LB-21)

Figure 41. Settlement Vs Normal Stress (LB-22)

Table 27. Consolidation Settlement at Center and Corner (LB-31)

Normal Stress (KN/m ²)	Primary Consolidation Settlement at Center, Layer- 3 (cm)	Primary Consolidation Settlement at Corner, Layer- 3 (cm)
100	0.45	0.34
300	2.45	1.8
500	4.9	3.55
800	9.2	6.59
1000	12.4	8.85

Table 28. Consolidation Settlement at Center and Corner (LB-32)

Normal Stress (KN/m ²)	Primary Consolidation Settlement at Center, Layer- 3 (cm)	Primary Consolidation Settlement at Corner, Layer- 3 (cm)
100	0.19	0.17
300	0.93	0.83
500	1.73	1.54

800	3.05	2.69
1000	4	3.52

The figure 42 shows the graph for settlement difference between corner and center at Location 3, borehole 1. The figure 43 shows the graph for settlement difference between corner and center at Location 3, borehole 2.

Figure 42. Settlement Vs Normal Stress (LB-31)

Figure 43. Settlement Vs Normal Stress (LB-32)

We have calculated the result obtained from applying normal stress 100 KN/m² to 1000 KN/m² to a strip footing to observe the different value of consolidation settlement in the center and corner of the foundation. The statistical analysis is given table 29 which shows the values of standard deviation, mean, intercept and slope.

Table 29. Consolidation Settlement at Corner

Normal Stress (KN/m ²)	L1B1	L1B2	L2B1	L2B2	L3B1	L3B2	Mean	Standard Deviation
100	0.23	0.25	0.08	0.26	0.34	0.17	0.22	0.088
300	1.1	1.19	0.4	1.33	1.8	0.83	1.11	0.472
500	2	2.16	0.72	2.48	3.55	1.54	2.08	0.946
800	3.39	3.67	1.2	4.34	6.59	2.69	3.65	1.795
1000	4.35	4.71	1.53	5.66	8.85	3.52	4.77	2.436
Intercept	-0.26	-0.282	-0.083	-0.433	-0.911	-0.263	-0.372	
Slope	0.004	0.0050	0.0016	0.0060	0.0095	0.0037	0.005	

The following table shows the primary consolidation settlement at corner of the foundation in centimeters. The maximum consolidation value was observed 8.85 cm at 1000 KN/m² and minimum consolidation value was observed 0.08 cm at 100 KN/m² stress. The slope is 0.005 cm which is as same as center so the increase in settlement is same as center.

Variation of Pressure Increment Due to Change in Normal Stress

The table 30-35 shows value of pressure increment for normal stress in different types of location of Bangladesh.

Table 30. Value of Pressure Increment (LB-11)

Normal Stress (KN/m ²)	Pressure Increment (KN/m ²)
100	2.12
300	10.156
500	18.145
800	30.127
1000	38.115
1500	50.085

Table 31. Value of Pressure Increment (LB-12)

Normal Stress (KN/m ²)	Pressure Increment (KN/m ²)
100	2.22
300	10.4
500	18.58
800	30.85
1000	39.03
1500	59.48

The figure 44 shows the graph for pressure increment for different normal stress at Location 1, borehole 1. The figure 45 shows the graph for pressure increment for different normal stress at Location 1, borehole 2.

Figure 44. Pressure increment Vs Normal Stress (LB-11)

Figure 45. Pressure increment Vs Normal Stress (LB-12)

Table 32. Value of Pressure Increment (LB-21)

Normal Stress (KN/m ²)	Pressure Increment, Layer- 4 (KN/m ²)	Pressure Increment, Layer- 5 (KN/m ²)
100	1.541	0.92
300	7.76	4.63
500	13.99	8.34
800	23.325	13.91
1000	29.55	17.62
1500	45.11	26.89

Table 33. Value of Pressure Increment (LB-22)

Normal Stress (KN/m ²)	Pressure Increment, Layer- 3 (KN/m ²)	Pressure Increment, Layer- 4 (KN/m ²)
100	4.23	2.01
300	20.545	9.77
500	36.85	17.53
800	61.326	29.168
1000	77.639	36.093
1500	118.42	56.324

The figure 46 shows the graph for pressure increment for different normal stress at Location 2, borehole 1. The figure 47 shows the graph for pressure increment for different normal stress at Location 2, borehole 2.

Figure 46. Pressure increment Vs Normal Stress (LB-21)

Figure 47. Pressure increment Vs Normal Stress (LB-22)

Table 34. Value of Pressure Increment (LB-31)

Normal Stress (KN/m ²)	Pressure Increment, Layer- 2 (KN/m ²)	Pressure Increment, Layer- 3 (KN/m ²)
100	27.8	13.61
300	130.6	63.75
500	233.36	113.89
800	387.46	189.11
1000	490.1	239.56
1500	747.05	364.6

Table 35. Value of Pressure Increment (LB-32)

Normal Stress (KN/m ²)	Pressure Increment, Layer- 2 (KN/m ²)	Pressure Increment, Layer- 3 (KN/m ²)
100	10.975	4.446
300	51.41	20.96
500	91.844	37.4
800	152.46	62.1
1000	192.93	78.56
1500	294.016	119.73

The figure 48 shows the graph for pressure increment for different normal stress at Location 3, borehole 1. The figure 49 shows the graph for pressure increment for different normal stress at Location 3, borehole 2.

Figure 48. Pressure increment Vs Normal Stress (LB-31)

Figure 49. Pressure increment Vs Normal Stress (LB-32)

We have applied normal stress 100 KN/m² to 1000 KN/m² and compared the stress increase at the clay layer. The statistical analysis is given in table 36 which shows the values of standard deviation, mean, intercept and slope.

Table 36. Pressure Increment Table

Normal Stress (KN/m ²)	L1B1	L1B2	L2B1	L2B2	L3B1	L3B2	Mean	Standard Deviation
100	2.12	2.22	0.92	2.01	13.61	4.446	4.22	4.741
300	10.2	10.4	4.63	9.77	63.75	20.96	19.95	22.109
500	18.1	18.58	8.34	17.53	113.89	37.4	35.64	39.492
800	30.12	30.85	13.91	29.168	189.11	62.1	59.21	65.555
1000	38.11	39.03	17.62	36.093	239.56	78.56	74.83	83.131
Intercept	-1.847	-1.870	-0.937	-1.646	-2.660	-3.766	-2.121	
Slope	0.040	0.041	0.019	0.038	0.251	0.082	0.078	

The following table shows the pressure increment in KN/m² for stress in the foundation at 100 to 1000 KN/m². Table shows a minimum increment of 0.91 KN/m² and maximum pressure increment of 239 KN/m² at 1000 KN/m² pressure on top of foundation.

Variation of consolidation settlement due to change in layer thickness

The table 37-42 shows consolidation settlement values for different layer thickness in different types of location of Bangladesh.

Table 37. Consolidation Settlement Values for Different Layer Thickness (LB-11)

Normal Stress (KN/m ²)	Layer Thickness (m)	Primary Consolidation Settlement (cm)	Secondary Consolidation Settlement in 10 Years (cm)
500	1.5	0.9	0.6
500	2	1.12	0.8
500	3	1.5	1.19
500	4	1.79	1.59
500	5	2.01	1.99
500	6	2.19	2.39
500	7	2.23	2.79

Table 38. Consolidation Settlement Values for Different Layer Thickness (LB-12)

Normal Stress (KN/m ²)	Layer Thickness (m)	Primary Consolidation Settlement (cm)	Secondary Consolidation Settlement in 10 Years (cm)
500	1.5	0.96	0.6

500	2	1.21	0.8
500	3	1.6	1.19
500	4	1.9	1.59
500	5	2.13	1.99
500	6	2.31	2.3
500	7	2.45	2.79

The figure 50 shows the graph for consolidation settlement vs layer thickness at Location 1, borehole 1. The figure 51 shows the graph for consolidation settlement vs layer thickness at Location 1, borehole 2.

Figure 50. Consolidation Settlement Vs Layer Thickness (LB-11)

Figure 51. Settlement Vs Layer Thickness (LB-12)

Table 39. Consolidation Settlement Values for Different Layer Thickness (LB-21)

Layer Thickness (Layer – 4) (m)	Primary Consolidation Settlement (cm)	Secondary Consolidation Settlement in 10 Years (cm)
1.5	0.31	0.3
2	0.39	0.4
4	0.66	0.8
6	0.84	1.2
7	0.91	1.4

Table 40. Consolidation Settlement Values for Different Layer Thickness (LB-22)

Layer Thickness (Layer – 4) (m)	Primary Consolidation Settlement (cm)	Secondary Consolidation Settlement in 10 Years (cm)
1	0.42	0.3
2	0.53	0.4
4	0.87	0.8
6	1.09	1.2
7	1.17	1.4

The figure 52 shows the graph for consolidation settlement vs layer thickness at Location 2, borehole 1. The figure 53 shows the graph for consolidation settlement vs layer thickness at Location 2, borehole 2.

Figure 52. Settlement Vs Layer Thickness (LB-21)

Figure 53. Settlement Vs Layer Thickness (LB-22)

Table 41. Consolidation Settlement Values for Different Layer Thickness (LB-31)

Layer Thickness (Layer – 2) (m)	Primary Consolidation Settlement (cm)	Secondary Consolidation Settlement in 10 Years (cm)
1.5	12.97	0.69
2	14.5	0.93
4	15.16	1.92
6	13.32	2.93
7	12.38	3.44

Table 42. Consolidation Settlement Values for Different Layer Thickness (LB-32)

Layer Thickness (Layer – 2) (m)	Primary Consolidation Settlement (cm)	Secondary Consolidation Settlement in 10 Years (cm)
1.5	14.9	0.89
2	16.5	1.25
4	17.16	1.56
6	19.32	2.93
7	20.8	4.44

The figure 54 shows the graph for consolidation settlement vs layer thickness at Location 3, borehole 1. The figure 55 shows the graph for consolidation settlement vs layer thickness at Location 3, borehole 2.

Figure 54. Settlement Vs Layer Thickness (LB-31)

Figure 55. Settlement Vs Layer Thickness (LB-32)

We have taken layer thickness of 1.5m to 5m to see the variation of primary and secondary consolidation settlement. The statistical analysis is given in table 43 which shows the values of standard deviation, mean, intercept and slope.

Table 43. Consolidation Settlement due to Change in Layer Thickness

Layer Thickness (m)	L1B1	L1B2	L2B1	L2B2	L3B1	L3B2	Mean	Standard Deviation
1.5	0.9	0.96	0.31	0.42	12.97	14.9	5.08	6.893
2	1.12	1.21	0.39	0.53	14.5	16.5	5.71	7.618
3	1.5	1.6	0.66	0.87	15.16	17.16	6.16	7.781
4	1.79	1.9	0.84	1.09	13.32	19.32	6.38	7.943
5	2.01	2.13	0.91	1.17	12.38	20.8	6.57	8.221
Intercept	0.478	0.528	0.057	0.112	14.690	12.745	4.768	
Slope	0.318	0.333	0.182	0.227	-0.330	1.61	0.390	

The table shows the primary consolidation settlement value in centimeter for change in layer thickness in meters. The maximum settlement 20.8 cm is found at 5 m thickness and minimum layer thickness of 0.31 cm is found in 1.5m thick clay layer.

Variation of Consolidation Settlement due to Change in D_f/B Ratio

The table 44-48 shows consolidation settlement values for different D_f/B ratio in different types of location of Bangladesh.

Table 44. Settlement Values for Different D_f/B ratio (LB-11)

D _f (m)	Width, B (m)	D _f / B ratio	Primary Consolidation Settlement (cm)
2.59	5.18	0.5	6.01
2.59	2.59	1	5.8
2.59	1.72	1.5	5.63
2.59	1.29	2	5.54

Table 45. Settlement Values for Different D_f/B ratio (LB-12)

D _f (m)	Width, B (m)	D _f / B ratio	Primary Consolidation Settlement (cm)
2.59	5.18	0.5	2.21
2.59	2.59	1	2.27
2.59	1.72	1.5	2.25
2.59	1.29	2	2.24

The figure 56 shows the graph for consolidation settlement Vs D_f/B ratio at Location 1, borehole 1. The figure 57 shows the graph for consolidation settlement Vs D_f/B ratio at Location 1, borehole 2.

Figure 56. Settlement Vs D_f/B ratio (LB-11)

Figure 57. Settlement Vs D_f / B Ratio (LB-12)

Distance between the bottom of the foundation to the E.G.L, (D_f) = 2.59 m.

Table 46. Settlement Values for Different D_f/B ratio (LB-21)

Width, B (m)	D_f / B ratio	Primary Settlement, Layer- 4 (cm)	Consolidation Settlement, Layer- 5 (cm)
5.18	0.5	0.86	1.26
2.59	1	0.83	1.24
1.72	1.5	0.81	1.22
1.29	2	0.8	1.21

Table 47. Settlement Values for Different D_f/B ratio (LB-22)

Width, B (m)	D_f / B ratio	Primary Settlement, Layer- 3 (cm)	Consolidation Settlement, Layer- 4 (cm)
5.18	0.5	4.69	1.32
2.59	1	4.38	1.28
1.72	1.5	4.16	1.24
1.29	2	4.03	1.22

The figure 58 shows the graph for consolidation settlement Vs D_f/B ratio at Location 2, borehole 1. The figure 59 shows the graph for consolidation settlement Vs D_f/B ratio at Location 2, borehole 2.

Figure 58. Settlement Vs D_f / B Ratio (LB-21)

Figure 59. Settlement Vs D_f / B Ratio (LB-22)

Distance between the bottom of the foundation to the E.G.L, (D_f) = 2.59 m. Increase the layer thickness(2nd) to 7m to observe variation.

Table 48. Settlement Values for Different D_f/B Ratio (LB-31)

Width, B (m)	D_f / B ratio	Primary Settlement, Layer- 2 (cm)	Consolidation Settlement, Layer- 3 (cm)
5.18	0.5	11.09	0.7
2.59	1	12.33	0.73
1.72	1.5	11.92	0.72
1.29	2	11.57	0.71

The figure 60 shows the graph for consolidation settlement Vs D_f/B ratio at Location 3, borehole 1.

Figure 60. Settlement Vs Df / B ratio (LB-31)

For shallow foundation the condition is D_f/B is less than or equal to 3. We have fixed the value of D_f to a recommended value and changed the foundation width to 1 to 5 meter and obtained following results. The statistical analysis is given in table 49 which shows the values of standard deviation, mean, intercept and slope.

Table 49. Consolidation Settlement Variation for Df/B Ratio

Df / B Ratio	L1B1	L1B2	L2B1	L2B2	L3B1	Mean	Standard Deviation
0.5	3.59	2.21	0.86	1.32	0.7	1.53	1.179
1	3.47	2.27	0.83	1.28	0.73	1.60	1.073
1.5	3.37	2.25	0.81	1.24	0.72	1.65	1.008
2	3.32	2.24	0.8	1.22	0.71	1.72	1.003
Intercept	3.665	2.225	0.875	1.350	0.710	1.765	
Slope	-0.182	0.014	-0.04	-0.068	0.004	-0.054	

The table shows the different values of primary consolidation settlement in centimeter for change in D_f/B ratio to 0.5 to 2. The maximum 2.24 cm settlement observed for D_f/B ratio 2 which indicate D_f of 2.59 m and width is 5.18 m where the applied load was 500 KN/m².

Variation of consolidation settlement due to change in footing size

The tables 50-55 show consolidation settlement values for different footing size in different types of location of Bangladesh.

Table 50. Settlement Values for Different Footing Size (LB-11)

No. of Observation	Footing Size (B × L) (m × m)	Primary Consolidation Settlement, Layer – 4 (cm)
1	1.5×1.5	2.05
2	3×3	2.1
3	5×5	2.01
4	7×7	1.75
5	9×9	4.42

Table 51. Settlement Values for Different Footing Size (LB-12)

No. of Observation	Footing Size (B × L) (m × m)	Primary Consolidation Settlement, Layer – 4 (cm)
1	1.5×1.5	2.22
2	3×3	2.28
3	5×5	2.17
4	7×7	1.89
5	9×9	1.53

The figure 61 shows the graph for consolidation settlement for different footing size at Location 1, borehole 1. The figure 62 shows the graph for consolidation settlement for different footing size at Location 1, borehole 2.

Figure 61. Consolidation Settlement Vs Number of Observation for Different Size of Footing (LB-11)

Figure 62. Consolidation Settlement Vs Number of Observation for Different Size of Footing (LB-12)

Table 52. Settlement Values for Different Footing Size (LB-21)

No. of Observation	Footing Size (B × L) (m × m)	Primary Consolidation Settlement, Layer – 4 (cm)	Primary Consolidation Settlement, Layer – 5 (cm)
1	1.5×1.5	0.49	0.73
2	3×3	0.5	0.73
3	5×5	0.48	0.72
4	7×7	0.43	0.67
5	9×9	0.37	0.61

Table 53. Settlement Values for Different Footing Size (LB-22)

No. of Observation	Footing Size (B × L) (m × m)	Primary Consolidation Settlement, Layer – 3 (cm)	Primary Consolidation Settlement, Layer – 4 (cm)
1	1.5×1.5	0.68	0.19
2	3×3	0.64	0.19
3	5×5	0.51	0.17
4	7×7	0.35	0.14
5	9×9	0.22	0.11

The figure 63 shows the graph for consolidation settlement for different footing size at Location 2, borehole 1. The figure 64 shows the graph for consolidation settlement for different footing size at Location 2, borehole 2.

Figure 63. Consolidation Settlement Vs Number of Observation for Different Footing size (LB-21)

Figure 64. Settlement Vs Footing Size (LB-22)

Table 54. Settlement Values for Different Footing Size (LB-31)

No. of Observation	Footing Size (B × L) (m × m)	Primary Consolidation Settlement, Layer – 2 (cm)	Primary Consolidation Settlement, Layer – 3 (cm)
1	1.5×1.5	9.96	4.17
2	3×3	13.07	4.9
3	5×5	8	3.68
4	7×7	4.22	1.66
5	9×9	2.64	1.21

Table 55. Settlement Values for Different Footing Size (LB-32)

No. of Observation	Footing Size (B × L) (m × m)	Primary Consolidation Settlement, Layer – 2 (cm)	Primary Consolidation Settlement, Layer – 3 (cm)
1	1.5×1.5	3.69	0.43
2	3×3	13.07	4.9
3	5×5	8	3.68
4	7×7	4.22	1.66
5	9×9	2.64	1.21

The figure 65 shows the graph for consolidation settlement for different footing size at Location 3, borehole 1. The figure 66 shows the graph for consolidation settlement for different footing size at Location 3, borehole 2.

Figure 65. Consolidation Settlement Vs Footing Size (LB-31)

Figure 66. Consolidation Settlement Vs Footing Size (LB-32)

Different footing size was for strip rectangular footing of size 1.5m × 1.5m to 9m × 9m. The constant stress 500 KN/m² was applied to see the variation in primary consolidation settlement. The statistical analysis is given in table 56 which shows the values of standard deviation, mean, intercept and slope.

Table 56. Consolidation Settlement Values for Different Footing Size

Footing Size (B × L) (m × m)	L1B1	L1B2	L2B1	L2B2	L3B1	L3B2	Mean	Standard Deviation
1.5 × 1.5	2.05	2.22	0.49	0.68	4.17	3.69	2.22	1.507
3 × 3	2.1	2.28	0.5	0.64	4.9	13.07	3.92	4.757
5 × 5	2.01	2.17	0.48	0.51	3.68	8	2.81	2.809
7 × 7	1.75	1.89	0.43	0.35	1.66	4.22	1.72	1.402
9 × 9	4.42	1.53	0.37	0.22	1.21	2.64	1.73	1.581
Intercept	1.149	2.549	0.547	0.843	5.872	9.609	3.428	
Slope	0.439	-0.177	-0.031	-0.121	-0.916	-1.095	-0.317	

The following table shows the different footing size in meters and consolidation values in centimeters. The maximum primary consolidation settlement was found for the footing size 3m × 3m, and 9m × 9m size footing shows minimum consolidation.

Effect of Bearing Surface Depth in Consolidation Settlement

The tables 57-62 show consolidation settlement values for different bearing surface depth in different types of location of Bangladesh.

Table 57. Settlement Values for Different Bearing Surface Depth (LB-11)

Bearing Surface Depth (m)	Primary Consolidation Settlement, Layer – 4 (cm)
1	1.67
2	1.92
3	2.24
4	2.67

Table 58. Settlement Values for Different Bearing Surface Depth (LB-12)

Bearing Surface Depth (m)	Primary Consolidation Settlement, Layer – 4 (cm)
1	1.81
2	2.08
3	2.43
4	2.9

The figure 67 shows the graph for consolidation settlement Vs bearing surface depth at Location 1, borehole 1. The figure 68 shows the graph for consolidation settlement Vs bearing surface depth at Location 1, borehole 2.

Figure 67. Consolidation Settlement Vs Depth (LB-11)

Figure 68. Consolidation Settlement Vs Bearing Surface Depth (LB-12)

Table 59. Settlement Values for Different Bearing Surface Depth (LB-21)

Bearing Surface Depth (m)	Primary Consolidation Settlement, Layer – 4 (cm)	Primary Consolidation Settlement, Layer – 5 (cm)
1	0.41	0.64
2	0.47	0.7
3	0.53	0.76
4	0.61	0.84

Table 60. Settlement Values for Different Bearing Surface Depth (LB-22)

Bearing Surface Depth (m)	Primary Consolidation Settlement, Layer – 3 (cm)	Primary Consolidation Settlement, Layer – 4 (cm)
1	1.95	0.62
2	2.41	0.71
3	3.07	0.83
4	4.07	0.98

The figure 69 shows the graph for consolidation settlement Vs bearing surface depth at Location 2, borehole 1. The figure 70 shows the graph for consolidation settlement Vs bearing surface depth at Location 2, borehole 2.

Figure 69. Consolidation Settlement Vs Bearing Surface Depth (LB-21)

Figure 70. Settlement Vs Bearing Surface Depth (LB-22)

Table 61. Settlement Values for Different Bearing Surface Depth (LB-31)

Bearing Surface Depth (m)	Primary Consolidation Settlement, Layer – 2 (cm)	Primary Consolidation Settlement, Layer – 3 (cm)
1	5.47	2.56
2	9.25	3.76
3	16.67	5.99
4	25.54	10.39

Table 62. Settlement Values for Different Bearing Surface Depth (LB-32)

Bearing Surface Depth (m)	Primary Consolidation Settlement, Layer – 2 (cm)	Primary Consolidation Settlement, Layer – 3 (cm)
1	7.66	1.19
2	11.4	1.49
3	18.41	1.94
4	31.58	2.64

The figure 71 shows the graph for consolidation settlement Vs bearing surface depth at Location 3, borehole 1. The figure 72 shows the graph for consolidation settlement Vs bearing surface depth at Location 3, borehole 2.

Figure 71. Consolidation Settlement Vs Bearing Surface Depth (LB-31)

Figure 72. Consolidation Settlement Vs Bearing Surface Depth (LB-32)

We took the bearing surface depth (D_r) 1m to 4m to see the variation in consolidation settlement. The stress was 500 KN/m². The statistical analysis is given in table 63 which shows the values of standard deviation, mean, intercept and slope.

Table 63. Settlement Values for Different Bearing Surface Depth

Bearing Surface Depth (m)	L1B1	L1B2	L2B1	L2B2	L3B1	L3B2	Mean	Standard Deviation
1	1.67	1.81	0.64	1.95	2.56	1.19	1.64	0.660
2	1.92	2.08	0.7	2.41	3.76	1.49	2.06	1.020
3	2.24	2.43	0.76	3.07	5.99	1.94	2.74	1.765
4	2.67	2.9	0.84	4.07	10.39	2.64	3.92	3.335
Intercept	1.295	1.400	0.570	1.120	-0.75	0.615	0.708	
Slope	0.332	0.362	0.066	0.702	2.572	0.48	0.752	

The table shows the different consolidation value for different borehole in centimeter and the bearing surface depth is changed from 1m to 4m. The maximum 10.39 consolidation settlement was seen at 4m bearing surface depth and minimum settlement was seen for minimum bearing surface depth.

RESULT ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Result Analysis

Statistical analysis will be done in following eight parameters for six boreholes in three locations:

- Change in consolidation settlement due to change in normal stress.
- Secondary Consolidation Settlement in Number of Years.
- Difference Between Settlement at Corner and Center of the Foundation.
- Variation of Pressure Increment Due to Change in Normal Stress.
- Variation of consolidation settlement due to change in layer thickness.

- Variation of consolidation settlement due to change in D_f/B ratio.
- Variation of consolidation settlement due to change in footing size.
- Effect of bearing surface depth in consolidation settlement.

Result Discussions

In the observation of change in consolidation settlement due to change in normal stress the standard deviation value is within 0.142 to 4.047, so we can say that the data is consistent and variation in data is not very high. The mean value is within 0.21 to 4.8. From the graph we have seen that there is strong positive correlation between the normal stress and consolidation settlement.

In the observation of secondary Consolidation Settlement in Number of Years the standard deviation value is within 1 to 1.5, so we can say that the data is very consistent and variation in data is not very high. The mean value is within 1 to 2.33 so the secondary consolidation settlement is within the limit. From the graph we have seen that the relation between the secondary consolidation settlement and number of years is nonlinear and logarithmic.

No clear relationship was established between the consolidation settlement and clay layer thickness. The analysis shows a high standard deviation value so the is not consistent. Unexpected and unpredictable behavior has been seen in the analysis.

In the observation of change in consolidation settlement due to change in normal stress at the corner of the foundation we have found the difference between the center and corner for maximum is 4 cm and minimum is 0.03cm. From the graph we have seen that there is strong positive correlation between the normal stress and consolidation settlement which is linear.

Result obtained from Variation of Pressure Increment Due to Change in Normal Stress shows a very high standard deviation of up to 84, so the data is not consistent which shows a negative intercept value and positive correlation.

The analysis of Variation of consolidation settlement due to change in D_f/B ratio shows the standard deviation value less than 2, so the data is consistent. Negative correlation was seen in the graph and the decrease in primary and secondary with the increase of D_f/B ratio is comparatively low.

In the observation of variation of consolidation settlement due to different footing size no linear relationship was seen. The standard deviation values are not consistent as expected from graph. The slope value is not acceptable because there is no clear linear relationship, but overall negative slope and positive intercept value was found.

Positive strong linear correlation was found between the bearing surface depth and primary consolidation settlement. The standard deviation value is 0.66 to 3.335 and the slope is 0.752 m and the intercept value are positive.

The consolidation settlement of the soil with only two clay layers has been observed less than 5 cm. In case of clay layer more than two the settlement value increase rapidly up to 40 cm settlement in maximum load so deep foundation is recommended.

Secondary consolidation settlement can cause damage the structure in long term. Statistical analysis shows that 5.07 cm settlement in 10 years. So, precaution should be taken in construction of foundation for long period of time because it might go significant amount of secondary consolidation settlement over the years.

Higher consolidation settlement values were observed for the load more than 800 KN/m^2 . So, we should limit the maximum footing load within the limit in soil with more clay layer and high-rise building is not commanded in soil layer with multiple clay layer.

We have observed an average of 239 KN/m^2 pressure increment for 1500 KN/m^2 stress in clay layer so at least 19% factor of safety must be included for pressure increment.

In shallow foundation when D_f/B is equal to 2 the analysis shows a fair amount of settlement, so D_f/B is up to 2 or higher is recommended for shallow foundation.

It is recommended to construct the foundation where the clay layer thickness is less. If clay layer thickness is higher it shows a very high consolidation settlement.

We observed from statistical analysis that minimum consolidation occurs for the maximum footing size in most cases, so bigger footing size is recommended in soil with multiple clay layer.

Minimum bearing surface depth is recommended for less primary consolidation settlement.

Research Findings

- Research shows that if we increase 1 KN/m^2 normal stress primary consolidation settlement increase 0.005 cm in both center and corner of the foundation.
- The P- value shows the level of marginal significance which is greater than 0.05 so the difference between primary consolidation settlement is not significant between the center and corner of the foundation.
- For $3\text{m} \times 3\text{m}$ strip footing 0.5% decrease in primary consolidation settlement at the corner has been seen in the analysis.
- When D_f/B ratio increase the consolidation settlement decrease. 1 unit increase in D_f/B ratio will decrease 0.054 unit decrease in consolidation settlement.
- An increase in clay layer shows the increase in consolidation settlement. 1m increase in clay layer has an increment of 0.39 cm of settlement.
- With the increase of footing size at first the primary consolidation settlement increase but after a certain point it decrease.
- As the footing size increase the primary consolidation settlement decrease. Although a straight linear relationship has not been seen in the analysis. In many cases unpredictable behavior has been seen in the analysis.
- Analysis shows an increase of 1 KN/m^2 normal stress can produce 0.078 KN/m^2 pressure increment in clay layer.
- Consolidation settlement increase with the increase of bearing surface depth. 1m increase in bearing surface depth increase 0.752cm consolidation settlement.
- There is a positive linear relationship between the pressure increment in clay layer for the applied normal stress.
- Secondary consolidation settlement is almost same at the center and corner of the foundation.
- Secondary consolidation settlement significantly changes with the change in layer thickness and number of years. According to Terzaghi logarithmic method secondary consolidation settlement starts from 2nd year at first year there is no secondary consolidation settlement.
- The variation in secondary consolidation settlement due to the change in normal stress, footing size and D_f/B ratio is almost negligible.
- There is no significant difference in consolidation settlement for change in length of foundation base, footing and column height.

CONCLUSION

Soil analysis is one on the most important part of the foundation engineering. Soil is a naturally occurring mixture of mineral and organic ingredients with a definite form, structure, and composition, therefore settlement of soil is essential. We must emphasize on the base of the substructure which is constructed on soil. In this research we have analyzed the consolidation settlement for different parameters. We obtained the desired result and statistical analysis which helped us establishing a relationship between soil and consolidation settlement.

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